

Modeling Language for Constructing Solvers in Machine Learning : Reductionist Perspectives

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Abstract—For a given specific problem an efficient algorithm has been the matter of study. However, an alternative approach orthogonal to this approach comes out, which is called a reduction. In general for a given specific problem this reduction approach studies how to convert an original problem into subproblems. This paper proposes a formal modeling language to support this reduction approach in order to make a solver quickly. We show three examples from the wide area of learning problems. The benefit is a fast prototyping of algorithms for a given new problem. It is noted that our formal modeling language is not intend for providing an efficient notation for data mining application, but for facilitating a designer who develops solvers in machine learning.

Keywords—Formal language, statistical inference problem, reduction.

I. INTRODUCTION

WHEN we use machine learning algorithms [10] as a software component in commercial applications, one of the typical difficulties has been the mechanism of achieving reliability. For example in an application such as speech recognition or handwritten digit recognition, the first question from public is usually related to the accuracies of their results. Traditionally this reliability has assessed by time consuming simulations. However recently, statistical learning methods, such as Support Vector Machines [4], kernel methods [15], and variational methods [6], made a revolution how to guarantee the reliability in a theoretical manner, which is achieved by bounds. Therefore in the perspectives of software reliability, statistical learning is the only promising clue at this moment, which should be emphasized. However, there are two immediate weaknesses.

Firstly the traditional approach to create a new algorithm for a new arising problem has disadvantageous in time and human power. Machine learning problems are continuously widening and deepening according as the expansion of application areas. All the more single problem requires various algorithms depending on the criteria, not only the efficiency in speed, but also efficiency in memory or power.

Secondly, the increase of the machine learning algorithms and target problems makes application designers more confused without using any synthetic design methodologies, such as the Unified Modeling Language (UML) in the area of software engineering. This is because there are several fundamental differences between the traditional methodology and that of machine learning. The first difference is the way that machine

learning bases on the algorithm induction. As we do not know how to write algorithm directly, machine learning algorithm learns its hypothesis from data. The second difference is that this process has two steps: a learning phase and an application phase (or training phase and test phase). Similarly, there are crucial differences in terms of decomposition of problems and the number of samples as well.

The first problem of continuously arising problems can be solved by a recent appeared reduction approach [8]. Traditionally, for a given specific target problem, the creation of a new algorithm is the matter of study. A reduction approach, which is orthogonal to this traditional approach, breaks down a problem into decomposed problems that can be solved by already known algorithms, such as classification algorithms. Together with the statistical learning perspective, if we derive overall bounds from individual bounds of decomposed subproblems, this could be the definitive advantage over the traditional approach although this paper does not show this point. For the second problem of paradigms the related work is in Allison [2]. Allison formalizes the sample complexity using a functional language Haskell. However, this approach does not say anything about other aspects which we mentioned before.

The contribution of this paper is 1) to construct a formal modeling language in order to solve those two problems, and 2) to show several examples using this formal modeling language including new algorithms. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we show briefly our new programming paradigm and our summary of language in the following Section, including syntax and semantics of our modeling language. In Section 4 we show several examples using our modeling language and conclude.

II. INDUCTIVE INFERENCE PROGRAMMING PARADIGM

We introduce an inductive inference programming paradigm as the background of our formal modeling language. Firstly, we should separate an algorithm (or function) from an input, while in the procedural language an algorithm is directly connected with an input. This would be natural because machine learning learns from data, whereas these data consist of not only input data but also output data. At the same time, this would be natural because we are in difficulties in writing algorithms directly, which is the reason why we use machine learning methods to 'learn' them. Secondly, we should represent both of two phases, which consist of a training phase and a test phase. The learning algorithms learn hypotheses from data, but usually the second phase that uses

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these hypotheses fulfills the function in an application. In sum, a schema 1) shows a form of a traditional procedural language and 2) shows that of ours.

- 1) Output algorithm(Input)
- 2) $\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{Algorithm} \\ \text{TestOutput} | \text{TestInput} \sim \text{TrainingInput} \end{array} \right\rangle$

III. OUR MODELING LANGUAGE

The aim of our modeling language is to describe (inductive / statistical) inference problems in the area of machine learning, especially to describe the necessary and sufficient input / output information. Therefore based on the inductive inference programming paradigm we introduced above, we can formalize this problem description as a specification of a problem. The core of this modeling language is to introduce A) the notation of data structures, B) relationships between those data structures, especially inference relations, C) rewriting rules between problems, and D) semantics of rewriting rules, especially related to the number of samples.

A. Data Structures

We introduce a sequence and a (directed) graph. Although we do not describe an undirected graph in here for the sake of brevity, it is a direct extension of our framework. For a sequence we denote by $\prod_{i=1}^n X$ a sequence $\{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n\}$. For a (directed) graph we denote by $(\mathbf{G}.P)$ a pair of a DAG $\mathbf{G} = (X, E)$ and a joint probability distribution P of the random variables in some set X , where X is a finite and nonempty set whose elements are called nodes, and E is a set of ordered pairs of distinct elements of X . Sometimes in order to emphasize that the nodes in a DAG comprise X_i , we write $(\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$ instead of $(\mathbf{G}.P)$.

TABLE I
 DATA STRUCTURES IN OUR MODELING LANGUAGE

symbols	meaning
data structures	
X_i	i-th sample of X
$X_{(i)}$	i-th variable in X
$\prod X_i$	a sequence of observation
$(\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$	a pair of a DAG of samples X in topological order and correspondent probabilities.
$(\mathbf{G}(X_{(i)}.P)$	a pair of a DAG of variables in X in topological order and correspondent probabilities.
$\cup X_{(i)}$	union of variables

B. Relationships between Data Structures (Problem)

The summary of notation is shown in Table I and II. Among them we define by ' \sim ' the (inductive / statistical) inference relations, which is a natural extension of ' $x \sim N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ '. This notation compresses a training and a test process. Firstly, training examples are put at the right-hand side and a resulting hypothesis is put at the left-hand side. We will use capital letters for training examples (which signifies random variables) and lower case letters for test examples (which signifies values

of random variables). Secondly, a test example is shown in the second element at the left-hand side and the name of the output by this test example is in the first element. This notation does not lose the implication of the number of samples. Now we show several examples.

TABLE II
 RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN DATA STRUCTURES

symbols	meaning
inductive inference relations	
$a \sim B$	an hypothesis a is (inductively / statistically) inferred by the given training set B .
$a_1 a_2 \sim B$	an hypothesis $a_1 a_2$ which Outputs a_1 for the given test example a_2 is (inductively / statistically) inferred by the given training set B .
$a \sim B_1 B_2$	an hypothesis a is (inductively / statistically) inferred by the training set B_1 , each of which is given with a label B_2 or a model B_2 .
relations between observations	
\vee	OR of observation
\cdot	multi-view of observation
independencies	
$\perp\!\!\!\perp$	independencies in observation
$(\mathbf{G}(X_i).P) \perp\!\!\!\perp_{\mathcal{M}} (\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$	$(\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$ satisfies the Markov condition.

Example 1 (Classification problem): A classification problem is defined as ' $y|x \sim X|Y$ '.

In this case, an hypothesis $y|x$ which outputs y for the given test example x is (inductively / statistically) inferred by the given training set X , each of which is given with the label Y .

A clustering problem is to place a label y for the given test example x based on the observation X [15] [14], usually with assuming the resulting cluster number c . It is noted that some classical clustering algorithm such as k-means clustering may not place labels on new test example, but only on training examples, which may easily be extended.

Example 2 (Clustering): A clustering problem is defined as ' $y|x \sim X$ '. ($y \in Y, Y = \{1, \dots, c\}$ when c is known).

A sequential prediction problem is defined in Conditional Random Fields (CRF) [7]. In a training phase, we take a sequence of words with labels $\prod(X|Y)$ as training examples. In a test phase, we predict a sequence of labels $\prod y$ based on the test sequence of words $\prod x$. In summary,

Example 3 (Sequential prediction): A sequential prediction problem is defined as ' $\prod(y|x) \sim \prod(X|Y)$ '.

Using Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) we can solve a couple of different kinds of problems. One problem is solved by the Viterbi algorithm [13], which associates an optimal sequence of states to a sequence of observations, given the parameters of a model of HMMs. More formally, for a given model $(\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$ and a sequence of observations $\prod_{y_i \in Y} y_i$, we choose the optimal state sequence $\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i$.

Example 4 (Path selection): A path selection problem is defined as ' $(\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i) | (g(x_i).p) \sim \prod_{Y_i \in Y} Y_i | (\mathbf{G}(X_i).P)$ '.

We show various problems in Table VI.

C. Syntax of Rewriting Rules

From now on we consider a problem with an algorithm. Rewriting rules are shown in Table III and IV, where an

arrow shows a transition. There are several categories of rewriting rules: 1) \vee (logical 'OR'), 2) independencies, and 3) dimensionality transformation. An algorithm might be altered when examples are split in the case of the rewriting rule (1), and when different hypotheses are merged in the case of the rewriting rule (13) and (14). It is noted that one famous example that uses sequence dimensional reduction is CRFs [7].

TABLE III

REWRITING RULES WHERE WE HANDLE PROBLEMS WITH ALGORITHMS

	rewriting rules
1	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim (B \vee C) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ H_1 = (a \sim B) \end{array} \right\rangle \vee \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ H_2 = (a \sim C) \end{array} \right\rangle \vee \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm B} \\ H = H_1 \vee H_2 \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[OR separation]</p>
2	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim B \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim (B \vee C) \end{array} \right\rangle$
3	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim B C \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim ((B_1 C_1) \vee (B_2 C_2)), (B_1 \cup B_2 = B) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[OR separation]</p>
4	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ \text{problem I} \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm B} \\ \text{problem I} \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[algorithm conversion]</p>
5	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x_{(i)} \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[equalization of training and test set]</p>
6	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ \Pi(y x) \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[sequence dim-reduction]</p>
7	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ (y x) \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ \Pi(y x) \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[sequence dim-augmentation]</p>
8	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ \Pi y (G\Pi x_i) \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[graph dim-reduction]</p>
9	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ \Pi y (G(\Pi x_i)) \sim \Pi(X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[graph dim-augmentation]</p>

D. Semantics of Rewriting Rules

Rewriting rules related to decomposition and merge has two semantics : 1) decomposition semantics and 2) semantics of the number of samples.

Decomposition semantics relates to the fact that we decompose the input or the output examples instead of algorithms. This is due to the fact that an algorithm in machine learning consists of learned hypotheses, which are usually not able to decompose, which is different from the traditional decomposition of algorithms, such as parallelization of algorithms. In this reason, correspondent algorithms when decomposed should be carefully chosen based on the original algorithm. Assume that we divide an original training set into two sets. After learning an individual training set, we have to choose carefully how to merge those two hypotheses, where there are many possibilities in this merge. Similarly, correspondent algorithms when merged should be carefully chosen. Semantics of the number of samples can be used for the calculation of overall bounds from individual bounds.

TABLE IV

REWRITING RULES CONTINUED FROM THE PREVIOUS TABLE

	rewriting rules
10	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ (\Pi_1^n y_i) x \sim X \Pi_1^n Y_i \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ ((\Pi_1^2 y_i) x \sim X \Pi_1^2 Y_i) \vee \dots \vee ((\Pi_{n-1}^n y_i) x \sim X \Pi_{n-1}^n Y_i) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>with $G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$ [decomposition by Markov property]</p>
11	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ (\bigcup_1^n y_{(i)}) x \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ (y_{(1)} x \sim X Y) \vee \dots \vee (y_{(n)} x \sim X Y) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>with $G(X_{(i)}) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$ [decomposition by d-separation]</p>
12	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x, p \sim X Y, P \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ y x \sim X Y \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[marginalization of hidden variables]</p>
13	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ ((y_i x_i) \sim \Pi(X_i Y_i)) \vee \dots \vee ((y_k x_k) \sim \Pi(X_k Y_k)) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm B} \\ \Pi_{i=i}^k(y x) \sim \Pi(X_i Y_i) \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[merge sequences]</p>
14	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ ((y_{(i)} x_{(i)}) \sim \Pi(X_{(i)} Y_{(i)})) \vee \dots \vee ((y_{(k)} x_{(k)}) \sim \Pi(X_{(k)} Y_{(k)})) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm B} \\ \bigcup_{i=i}^k (y x) \sim \bigcup_{i=i}^k X_i \bigcup_{i=i}^k Y_i \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[merge variables]</p>
15	$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim \bigcup X_{(i)} \bigcup Y_{(k)} (X_{(i)}, X_{(k)} \subseteq X) \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{algorithm A} \\ a \sim X \end{array} \right\rangle$ <p>[superset]</p>

IV. EXAMPLE OF REWRITING

In this section we show several examples of reduction of a source problem into a destination problem. The first example shows a parallelization of SVMs [11]. It is noted that there are many other ways to decompose this problem other than our examples.

Example 5: (Parallelization of SVMs) A problem $y|x \sim X|Y$ with $X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$, $X_{(i)} \perp\!\!\!\perp X_{(j)}$ with SVMs is equivalent to the following decomposed problems.

$$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ H_1 = y|x_1 \sim X_1|Y_1, \\ \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ H_2 = y|x_2 \sim X_2|Y_2, \\ \text{boosting algorithm} \\ y|x \sim H_1 \vee H_2, \end{array} \right\rangle$$

with $X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$, $X_{(i)} \perp\!\!\!\perp X_{(j)}$ and with $X_1 \Leftrightarrow X_2$, where Y_1 is a label for X_1 and Y_2 is a label for X_2 , and $X = X_1 \cup X_2$.

Rewriting Procedure 5: First we decompose examples X into X_1 and X_2 . It is noted that in the schema the number shows the number of rewriting rules in Tables.

$$\left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ y|x \sim X|Y \end{array} \right\rangle \rightarrow^{(4)} \left\langle \begin{array}{l} \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ y|(x_1 \vee x_2) \sim ((X_1|Y_1) \vee (X_2|Y_2)) \end{array} \right\rangle$$

$$\rightarrow_{(3)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ H_1 = y|x_1 \sim X_1|Y_1, \\ \text{SVMs algorithm} \\ H_2 = y|x_2 \sim X_2|Y_2, \\ \text{boosting algorithm} \\ y|x \sim H_1 \vee H_2, \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$$

Next example rewrites from a path selection problem into a sequential prediction problem.

Example 6: A path selection problem $(\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i | (g(x_i).p) \sim \prod Y_i | (G(X_i).P) (G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp_M)$ with the Viterbi algorithm can be reduced into a sequential prediction problem $PI(y|x) \sim \prod(X|Y) (G(X_{(i)}) \perp\!\!\!\perp_M)$ with CRF algorithm.

Rewriting Procedure 6: Using the rewriting rule (9), a path selection problem can be decomposed into the following problems:

$$\begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Viterbi algorithm} \\ (\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i | (g(x_i).p) \sim \prod Y_i | (G(X_i).P) \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{(def G)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Viterbi algorithm} \\ \prod(x_i) | \prod(x_i | p_i) \sim \prod Y_i | \prod(X_i | P_i) \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{D(10)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Viterbi algorithm} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_{i+1} | (x_i | p_i) \sim Y_i | (X_{i+1} | P_{i+1}) \\ \dots \\ x_k | (x_{k-1} | p_{k-1}) \sim Y_{k-1} | (X_k | P_k) \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{M(13)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CRF algorithm} \\ \prod(x_{i+1} | x_i, p_i) \sim (\prod Y_i | X_{i+1}, P_{i+1}) \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{(12)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CRF algorithm} \\ \prod(x_{i+1} | x_i) \sim (\prod(Y_i | X_{i+1})) \end{array} \right. \end{array}$$

V. OVERVIEW EXAMPLE

We first define a structure discovery problem. We define it as the combination of the learning Bayesian networks from data and the Bayesian inference using Bayesian networks. We denote by x_i the i th example and by $X_{(i)}$ the i th random variable. A Bayesian network is defined as a pair (G, p) , where $G = (V, E)$ is an acyclic directed graph.

Definition 1 (Structure Discovery + Inference) Problem: Let $S = \{x_1, \dots, x_m\}$ be training examples, where each x has d dimensions. The first phase is to learn a Bayesian networks from data, where we consider the problem of analyzing the distribution over a set of random variables $X_{(1)}, \dots, X_{(d)}$, based on a fully observed training examples where each x_i is a complete assignment to the variables $X_{(1)}, \dots, X_{(d)}$. The second phase is to determine various probabilities of interest based on the constructed Bayesian networks.

Now we show the overview example. Although there exists an algorithm for this structure discovery problem, we assume that we just come up our mind of this problem. Hence we assume that we have no solver for this problem in this world. Possible approaches are 1) to create a new algorithm for this problem (traditional approach), and 2) to take a reduction approach to decompose this problem into small subproblems. On one hand a traditional approach would be beneficial in that we might create an efficient solver for this problem, but it would take time and human power. On the other hand a reduction approach has two benefits in that we can immediately apply

this scheme (fast-prototyping) and that we can calculate the overall bounds of this problem using individual bounds if we apply a statistical learning in all of their solvers.

The first thing we should do is to decompose a problem into small subproblems. In this process when we can decompose using rewriting rules, we have to check the feasibility.

Example 7: A structure discovery problem $\bigcup_{j=\ell}^k x_{(j)} | \bigcup_{i=n}^m x_{(i)} \sim X (G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp_M)$ with an arbitrary structure discovery algorithm is equivalent to $\#(k-l)$ number of multi-class classification problems where we observe them in $\bigcup X_{(i)}$ with a classification algorithm (and the hypotheses merge with an arbitrary boosting algorithm).

Rewriting Procedure 7: Using the rewriting rule (10), a structure discovery problem $\bigcup_{j(j)} | \bigcup_{x(n)} \sim X$ can be decomposed in a following manner.

$$\begin{array}{l} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{arbitrary structure} \\ \text{discovery algorithm} \\ \bigcup_{j(j)} | \bigcup_{x(i)} \sim X \end{array} \right. \rightarrow_{D(11)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{arbitrary structure} \\ \text{discovery algorithm} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_{(l)} | x_{(n)} \sim X \\ \dots \\ x_{(l)} | x_{(m)} \sim X \\ \dots \\ x_{(k)} | x_{(n)} \sim X \\ \dots \\ x_{(k)} | x_{(m)} \sim X \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{(5)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{arbitrary structure} \\ \text{discovery algorithm} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_{(l)} | x \sim X | X_{(l)} \\ \dots \\ x_{(l)} | x \sim X | X_{(l)} \\ \dots \\ x_{(k)} | x \sim X | X_{(k)} \\ \dots \\ x_{(k)} | x \sim X | X_{(k)} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right. \\ \rightarrow_{M(14)} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{multiclass classification / regression} \\ H_j = x_{(l)} | x \sim X | X_{(l)} \\ \dots \\ \text{multiclass classification / regression} \\ H_k = x_{(k)} | x \sim X | X_{(k)} \\ \text{arbitrary merge algorithm} \\ H = H_j \vee \dots \vee H_k \end{array} \right. \end{array}$$

It is noted that if the value of $X_{(l)}, \dots, X_{(k)}$ is real we do regression, otherwise we do multiclass classification. As is shown above, this rewriting is done in a minute, while it would take at least a couple of months if we create a new solver. It is noted that in order to supply the training examples for above solvers, we need an efficient data converter.

Then we use this collective solvers to obtain results in Table V. We use $SV M^{light}$ on pentium III (800MHz) in the line 'comb', while for the comparison as an original solver we use the Probabilistic Network Library (PNL) at Intel in the line 'orig'. Datasets are from the UCI Machine Learning Repository and the Statlib dataset at CMU. Table shows that in all the items the original solver gives better results than ours in this case. On the other hands, our lines of codes are far less than the PNL, which should be emphasized, but this rewriting

is done in a minute if we have an efficient data converter, while it would take at least a couple of months if we create a new solver. Table also shows accuracies comparison and both approaches are quite comparable.

It is noted that our collective solvers assume that the existence of the base solvers from the beginning, which is SVM^{light} in this case. Otherwise our approach would lose the fundamental assumption. Therefore, some might argue that we should include the code size of SVM^{light} , which we believe that although in this case we omit this this is a fair comparison.

TABLE V
 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Lines of Codes	body	library	total
Ours (lines)	127	-	127
PNL (lines)	500	2400	2900

datasets / speed	# sam- ples	dim	comb- ined (ours) [s]	orig (PNL) [s]
alarm	10000	37	17	1
ionosphere	352	507	35	4
heart scale	270	13	1	0.2
breast cancer	699	10	1	0.2
iris	150	4	0.4	0.1
usps	2007	256	396	20
australian	690	15	2	0.4
dna	2000	180	185	10
diabetes	768	9	1	0.2
shuttle	43500	10	49	8
vehicle	846	9	56	0.5
$MNIST_{10000}$	10000	784	107	15

datasets / accu- racy	comb- ined (ours) [s]	orig (PNL) [s]
alarm	83.4	89.0
ionosphere	87.3	87.0
heart scale	86.2	84.2
breast cancer	95.0	92.0
iris	93.0	92.0
usps	91.0	93.3
australian	85.2	82.9
dna	80.0	83.3
diabetes	82.0	78.2
shuttle	79.9	82.4
vehicle	74.2	79.5
$MNIST_{10000}$	84.0	86.2

Finally we consider the overall bounds. As arbitrary classification problems are independent, an arbitrary merge algorithm is an 'OR combination' of these results in this case. Individual bounds of SVMs are

$$P_{D_i}(y \neq g(x)) \leq \frac{1}{l_{\gamma_i}} \sum_{j=1}^l \xi_j + \frac{4}{l_{\gamma_i}} \sqrt{tr(K_i)} + 3\sqrt{\frac{\ln(2/\delta_i)}{2l}}$$

from [15]. Hence using union bounds the overall bounds become

$$P_D(y \neq g(x)) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k P_{D_i}(y \neq g(x)) \leq \sum_{i=1}^k \left(\frac{1}{l_{\gamma_i}} \sum_{j=1}^l \xi_j + \frac{4}{l_{\gamma_i}} \sqrt{tr(K_i)} + 3\sqrt{\frac{\ln(2/\delta_i)}{2l}} \right).$$

We can calculate this figure. It is noted that as the number of solvers grows, the bounds become very loose, which is one of

the demerits of a reduction approach.

VI. CONCLUSION

The contribution of this paper is to construct a formal modeling language for a developer who write solvers in machine learning. The syntax and semantics of this formal modeling language are shown in Tables. We implement the interesting aspects in this formal language, which we named the inductive inference programming paradigm, such as training / test phase separation, decomposition semantics, and separation of an algorithm and input / output. Then we show three rewriting examples. These examples show that for a given new problem we might be able to rewrite a wide range of new problems into easier problems, such as classification problems. Therefore this reduction approach enables us to do a fast prototyping of algorithms for a new problem.

This reduction approach has several merits. Firstly, once we represent our problem by our modeling language, we can obtain a fast-prototyping solver, based on the simple solvers such as classification and boosting. However, this approach might not achieve an efficiency in terms of speed. Secondly, when we apply this method to statistical learning algorithms, we can easily guarantee the reliability of the results by the overall bounds. Then we can combine individual bounds of these solvers into overall bounds, which enables us to guarantee the overall reliability.

We implemented this reduction approach and did the experiments, which is shown in the overall example. We checked that our approach is far easier to implement without degrading its accuracies although it has demerit in the speed of execution. As is shown in the paper the result of rewriting boils down to the combination of easy algorithms in statistical learning, such as classification and boosting. Hence we can combine individual bounds of classification and boosting into overall bounds, which enables us to guarantee the overall reliability.

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TABLE VI

TABLE SHOWS AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF VARIOUS INDUCTIVE INFERENCE PROBLEMS IN MACHINE LEARNING: 1. MCMC, IMPORTANCE SAMPLING. 2. SPECTRAL CLUSTERING, 1-CLASS CLASSIFICATION, GAUSSIAN MIXTURE. 3. LEARNING BAYESIAN NETWORKS FROM DATA. 4. SEMI-SUPERVISED LEARNING. 5. SVM, BOOSTING, GAUSSIAN PROCESS. 6. M^3 -HMM, STRUCTURED CLASSIFICATION. 7. CRF. 8. BI-GRAM. 9. VITERBI. 10. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING. 11. CO-TRAINING. 12. [STEREOPSIS, LEARNING FUNDAMENTAL MATRIX]. 13. [STATISTICAL MACHINE TRANSLATION]. 14. [MEDICAL IMAGE REGISTRATION]. 15. TEXTURE PERCEPTION. 16. FACE RECOGNITION

	problems	Aim (inductive inference)	independence	correspondences
1-view problems				
1	sampling	$x \sim X$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	-
2	clustering	$y x \sim X$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	-
3	structure discovery	$\bigcup x_{(j)} \bigcup x_{(n)} \sim X$	$G(X_{(n)}) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$	-
4	semi-supervised learning	$y (x_1 \vee x_2) \sim ((X_1 Y) \vee (X_2))$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	-
5	classification	$y x \sim X Y$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	-
6	structured classification	$y x \sim \Pi(X Y)$	$G(X_{(i)}) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$	-
7	sequential prediction	$\Pi(y x) \sim \Pi(X Y)$	$G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$	-
8	sequential prediction	$\Pi(y x) \sim \Pi(X Y)$	$G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp 2$	-
9	path selection	$(\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i) (g(x_i).p) \sim$ $\prod_{Y_i \in Y} Y_i (G(X_i).P)$	$G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$	-
10	path selection	$(\prod_{x_i \in X} x_i) (g(x_i).p) \sim (R \vee$ $\prod_{Y_i \in Y} Y_i) (G(X_i).P)$	$G(X_i) \perp\!\!\!\perp M$	-
2-view problems				
11	co-training	$y (x_1, x_2) \vee x_3 \sim ((X_1, X_2 Y) \vee X_3)$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$X_1 \leftrightarrow X_2$
12	disparity	$f x_1, x_2 \sim X_1, X_2 C$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$X_1 \not\leftrightarrow X_2$
13	matching search	$x_1 x_2, corpus \sim X_1, X_2 Corpus$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$X_1 \not\leftrightarrow X_2$
14	registration	$c x_1, x_2 \sim X_1, X_2$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$X_1 \not\leftrightarrow X_2$
hierarchical problems				
15	texture perception	$((t bar, spot) \vee (bar x_1) \vee (spot x_2)) \sim$ $((X_1 Bar) \vee (X_2 Spot) \vee (Bar, Spot T))$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$Bar \not\leftrightarrow Spot$
16	cascade classification	$((f e, n, m) \vee (e x_1) \vee (n x_2) \vee (m x_3)) \sim$ $((X_1 E) \vee (X_2 N) \vee (X_3 M) \vee$ $(Eye, Nose, Mouth Face))$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	Eye $\not\leftrightarrow$ $Nose$ $Nose$ $\not\leftrightarrow$ $Mouth$ $Mouth$ $\not\leftrightarrow$ Eye
distributed problems				
17	distributed classification	$y x_1, x_2 \sim ((y x_1 \sim X_1 Y) \vee (y x_2 \sim$ $X_2 Y))$	$X_i \perp\!\!\!\perp X_j$	$X_1 \leftrightarrow X_2$